

Table continued.

Locality	1993-94			1994-95			1995-96				
	Samples tested (no.)	Fungi	% range	Samples tested (no.)	Fungi	% range	Samples tested (no.)	Fungi	% range		
Sahiwal	6	<i>Pyricularia oryzae</i>	0.5	5	–	0.0	7	–	0.0		
		<i>Rhizoctonia oryzae</i>	0.0 - 5.8		–	0.0		–	0.0		
		<i>Stemphylium</i> sp.	0.0 - 1.0		–	0.0		<i>Stemphylium</i> sp.	0.5		
		<i>Trichoconis padwickii</i>	5.8 - 14.8			<i>T. padwickii</i>		3.8 - 13.0		<i>T. padwickii</i>	2.0 - 5.7
		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 2.5			<i>B. oryzae</i>		0.0 - 2.0		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.5 - 1.0
		<i>C. lunata</i>	0.0 - 2.0			<i>C. lunata</i>		0.0 - 1.5		<i>C. lunata</i>	0.0 - 4.0
D.I. Khan	5	<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 2.5	4	<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 2.5	4	<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 1.0		
		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.0 - 3.0		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.0 - 2.5		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.0 - 1.5		
		<i>T. padwickii</i>	2.0 - 9.0		<i>T. padwickii</i>	1.0 - 6.0		<i>T. padwickii</i>	0.5 - 3.0		
		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.5 - 1.5		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.5 - 1.5		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 1.5		
		<i>C. lunata</i>	1.5 - 14.5		<i>C. lunata</i>	0.5 - 5.0		<i>C. lunata</i>	0.0 - 4.0		
Hyderabad	5	<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 2.5	5	<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.5 - 2.0	4	<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 1.0		
		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.5		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.5 - 2.0		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.0 - 2.0		
		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 1.0		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 0.5		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 0.5		
		<i>C. lunata</i>	0.0 - 1.0		<i>C. lunata</i>	0.0 - 27.0		<i>C. lunata</i>	0.0 - 21.0		
		<i>F. equiseti</i>	0.0 - 0.5		–	0.0		–	0.0		
		<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 1.0		<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 1.0		<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 2.5		
		<i>F. solani</i>	0.0 - 0.5		<i>F. solani</i>	0.0		–	0.0		
		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.0 - 0.5		–	0.0		–	0.0		
		<i>N. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 1.0		–	0.0		–	0.0		
		<i>Phoma</i> sp.	0.5 - 1.5		–	0.0		–	0.0		
		<i>Stemphylium</i> sp.	0.5		–	0.0		–	0.0		
		<i>T. padwickii</i>	6.5 - 11.0		<i>T. padwickii</i>	2.0 - 5.0		<i>T. padwickii</i>	1.0 - 4.0		
		Sukkur	5		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 4.5		(–)	14	<i>B. oryzae</i>	1.0 - 19.5
<i>C. lunata</i>	0.0 - 0.5					<i>C. lunata</i>	0.5 - 3.5				
<i>F. equiseti</i>	0.0 - 1.0					–	0.0				
<i>F. moniliforme</i>	3.0 - 6.0					<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.5 - 1.5				
<i>F. semitectum</i>	2.5 - 3.0					<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.0 - 2.5				
<i>N. oryzae</i>	0.5 - 1.0					<i>N. oryzae</i>	0.5 - 1.0				
<i>Phoma</i> sp.	0.0 - 0.5					<i>Phoma</i> sp.	0.5				
<i>Stemphylium</i> sp.	0.0 - 1.0					<i>Stemphylium</i> sp.	0.0 - 0.5				
<i>T. padwickii</i>	3.5 - 12.5					<i>T. padwickii</i>	1.5 - 10.0				
Total	41				19		37				

and *P. oryzae* prevailed in the Lahore area only. *Fusarium equiseti* was recorded only on seed from Hyderabad and Sukkur. Fewer seed-borne fungi were observed in seed samples from D.I. Khan. The involvement of *C. oryzae*, *Nigrospora oryzae*, *Phoma* sp.,

Rhizoctonia oryzae, and *Stemphylium* sp. in actual disease development has not yet been demonstrated.

Seed health testing is important to control crop diseases. The use of chemical seed treatment to improve seed quality and planting value has already

been reported. Considering the prevalence and incidence of fungal pathogens in rice seed lots, Pakistan's seed health certification program should include fungicide treatment of prebasic seeds to control field diseases. ■

Integrated pest management — other pests

Pratylenchus zeae in upland rice as influenced by ratio of intercropped maize

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In West Africa, maize is commonly relayed or intercropped with upland rice in traditional low-input systems. The density of maize as an intercrop may vary depending on many factors, including individual farmer preferences and country or region. Some nematodes that parasitize rice are common to maize, notably *Pratylenchus*

zeae, which is a pest of both crops. This study was done to examine the influence of maize - rice intercropping on the population density of *P. zeae* in rice.

Nematode densities were recorded in a trial at WARDA, established to monitor the influence of crop ratios on the incidence of stem borer pests on upland rice. The migratory endoparasite *P. zeae* and the ectoparasite *Helicotylenchus dihystrera* were present in

the trial area. The trial was first established in Jun 1995, continued for two successive seasons, and was irrigated when necessary. Nematode sampling was conducted on three occasions: at maturity of the second season, at 40 d after sowing (DAS), and at maturity of the third season. Nematode populations from rice and maize in the different treatments were compared (see table). Populations at maturity across all treatments, combined by crop, were also compared (see figure).

Five maize plants and 5 hills of rice with soil were removed from each plot and bulked. Nematodes were extracted from a 100-mL soil and 5-g root subsample using the modified tray method.

Maize cv EV 8744 SR (BC6F2B # Sine' 94B [110-d duration] and rice WAB 56-50 [115-d duration]) were direct-sown at 3 and 5 seeds hill⁻¹, respectively, on 12 × 12-m plots. Treatments were arranged in a randomized block design with four replications. The same design was retained throughout sole crops and maize-rice intercrops at ratios of 1:3 and 1:5. Treatment effects on nematode population densities were analyzed with two-way ANOVA.

Results indicated that intercropping with maize had no significant effect on the population density of *P. zeae* in rice roots. Furthermore, although maize is clearly a very good host for *P. zeae* (see figure), intercropping did not increase the population density of the nematode in either rice or maize in the second consecutive year of the trial.

In contrast, *P. zeae* numbers in soil from the rhizosphere of rice increased as the proportion of maize in the mixture increased ($P < 0.01$) (see table). This increase in soil population

Mean nematode populations recovered from maize and rice plants under different ratios of intercrop.^a

Nematode	Maize:rice	2nd season (maturity)		3rd season (40 DAS)		3rd season (maturity)	
		Maize	Rice	Maize	Rice	Maize	Rice
<i>P. zeae</i> (5 g roots)	1:0	815	–	23	–	602	–
	1:3	1210	455	32	14	968	353
	1:5	1330	282	22	15	975	213
	0:1	–	240	–	19	–	220
	LSD	646	236	27	18	421	143
<i>P. zeae</i> (100 mL soil)	1:0	603	–	73	–	443	–
	1:3	735	106*	33	10	492	59*
	1:5	590	28	130	13	428	24
	0:1	–	0	–	15	–	6
	LSD	687	64	97	14	269	47

* = significantly different ($P < 0.05$ from rice monocrop), – = not sampled.

Mean nematode densities for 100 mL soil and 5 g root

** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$; ns = not significant at $P < 0.05$.

***Pratylenchus zeae* and *Helicotylenchus dihystrera* densities: combined treatments for rice and maize sampled at maturity in the 2nd and 3rd cropping seasons.**

densities of *P. zeae* likely resulted from the migration of nematodes from heavily infested and senescing roots of neighboring maize crops at maturity. The impact of this migration on rice growth is likely to be greater where maize is sown early and harvested early in the rice season, as is often the

case in West Africa, thereby releasing high populations of nematodes to invade rice roots. *P. zeae* is a recognized pest of both crops and is responsible for production losses. Using cultivars that express tolerance for resistance to nematodes would therefore be an advantage for these low-input systems. ■

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